

White stem borer (WSB) effect on upland yield

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We studied the effect of WSB *Scirpophaga innotata* on upland rice with seven levels of protection in an experiment at the Makariki Experimental Farm, Seram Island, May-Aug 1982. IR36 was planted in a 5 × 5 m plot at 25 × 25 cm plant spacing in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Fertilizers as urea, TSP, and KCl were applied at 120 kg N, 40 kg P, and 50 kg K/ha. Half the N and all the P and K were applied in the row at the side of the plants 7 d after planting (DP). Half the N was applied 40 DP.

Yield loss caused by WSB *S. innotata* under upland conditions. Makariki, Seram Island, Indonesia, 1982.

Treatment ^a	WSB damage ^b (%)				Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield loss ^c (%)
	3 WP	5 WP	7 WP	9 WP		
1. Complete protection	7.2	1.2	1.5	1.9	2.4	—
2. Complete protection minus a	11.4	1.5	2.0	2.3	2.4	1.7
3. Complete protection minus b	21.9	7.9	4.4	3.3	1.8	25.6
4. Complete protection minus c	24.2	8.9	2.7	3.3	1.8	25.6
5. Complete protection minus d	14.4	2.1	3.4	3.3	2.3	5.8
6. Recommended ^d protection	12.5	2.2	2.3	2.6	2.2	9.1
7. No protection (control)	39.2	15.5	8.6	9.7	1.8	26.9
LSD (0.05)	2.7	1.2	0.6	0.6	0.4	—
CV (%)	9.7	14.6	11.2	9.9	14.6	—

^a a = seed treatment with carbaryl 85 S, b = carbofuran 3G (10 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (21 DP), c = carbofuran 3G (42 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (63 DP), d = monocrotophos 15 WSC. ^b WP = weeks after planting. ^c Compared with complete protection. Carbofuran 3G (10 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (when deadhearts exceeded 10%).

WSB damage at active tillering 3 wk after planting was high, an average 39.2% in control (see table). As plants grew, damage decreased.

Complete protection yielded 2.4 t/ha,

significantly higher than control, no protection during active tillering (treatment 3), and no protection at booting (treatment 4). □

Weed management

Effect of herbicides on *Ischaemum rugosum*

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Ischaemum rugosum Salisb., reported to be a major weed of partially irrigated and rainfed lowland rice in Thailand, Sri Lanka, and the Philippines, is very competitive against rice.

We designed a greenhouse experiment to study the effect of some herbicides on growth of *I. rugosum* under dry seeded and wet seeded conditions. There were 12 treatments in the dry seeded trial and 9 treatments in the wet seeded (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications.

Plant height and shoot dry weight were measured 6 wk after seeding. Under dry seeded conditions, both plant height and shoot dry weight were reduced by all the herbicides at all application times (see table). Even though propanil applied at the two- and

Effect of different herbicide treatments on shoot dry weight and height of *I. rugosum* 6 wk after seeding under simulated dry seeded and wetland conditions. ^a

Herbicide and application rate (kg ai/ha)	Time of application	Shoot weight (mg/plant)	Plant height (mm)
<i>Dry seeded</i>			
Butachlor (2.0)	Preemergence	0.6 b	5 ab
	1-leaf	2.9 d	22 c
	2-leaf	5.0 f	48 d
Thiobencarb (3.0)	Preemergence	1.2 c	7 ab
	1-leaf	3.3 de	24 c
	2-leaf	4.3 ef	46 d
Pendimethalin (2.0)	Preemergence	0.4 a	3 a
	1-leaf	3.0 d	22 c
	2-leaf	5.6 b	44 d
Propanil (2.0)	2-leaf	1.4 c	43 d
	3-leaf	0.5 ab	18 bc
Untreated	—	21.6 g	247 d
<i>Wetland</i>			
Butachlor (1.0)	Preemergence	0 a	—
	1-leaf	119.9 c	42 a
	2-leaf	119.6 c	54 b
Thiobencarb (1.0)	Preemergence	0 a	—
	1-leaf	112.7 bc	44 a
	2-leaf	67.2 b	52 b
Propanil (2.0)	2-leaf	0 a	—
	3-leaf	0 a	—
Untreated	—	124.6 c	156 c

^a In a column under each condition, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

three-leaf stages killed all weeds, some seedlings emerged after its application. Repeated applications may be needed to achieve complete weed kill.

Preemergence applications of butachlor, thiobencarb, and pendimethalin were superior to postemergence applications.

Under wet seeded conditions, preemergence applications of butachlor and thiobencarb, and propanil

application at the two- and three-leaf stages killed *I. rugosum*. Flooding a few days after treatment increased the effect of the preemergence treatments and, with propanil, prevented further weed seedling emergence. Butachlor and thiobencarb applied at the one- and two-leaf stages were not as effective as under dry seeded conditions. Herbicide uptake by the plant seems to be more

effective under dry seeded conditions because the herbicide is more easily leached down into the root zone.

Butachlor applied at the one- and two-leaf stages did not reduce shoot weight. Thiobencarb applied at the two-leaf stage reduced shoot weight. All plants that survived butachlor and thiobencarb treatments were stunted. □

Weed, management in rainfed rice - lentil crop sequence

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Rice - lentil is a widely adopted rainfed crop sequence in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Weed control affects yields.

We conducted a field trial 1985-86 and 1987-88 cropping years. Seven treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was sandy loam with

19.86% field capacity, 5.18% wilting point, 0.32% organic C, 160 kg available N/ha, 15 kg available P/ha, 166 kg available K/ha, and pH 7.7. EC was 0.104 dS/m at 25 °C, bulk density 1.47 g/cc, and water-holding capacity 33.1%. Akashi rice and Pant 209 lentil were the test varieties.

Table 1. Effect of weed control method on weed dry weight and yield of rice and lentil at B.H.U., Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Rice						Lentil					
	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)		Yield (t/ha)				Weed dry weight (g/m ²)		Yield (t/ha)			
	1985-86	1987-88	Grain		Straw		1985-86	1987-88	Grain		Straw	
			1985-86	1987-88	1985-86	1987-88			1985-86	1987-88	1985-86	1987-88
T1 Sowing of both crops with normal tillage and no weed control in either	403	280	0.4	0.4	2.6	3.5	113	163	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.5
T2 Farmer's method (2 hand weedings in both crops)	253	149	2.1	3.0	3.4	5.4	63	89	1.0	1.3	1.5	1.9
T3 Interculture twice by dryland weeder in both crops	325	241	0.9	1.6	3.0	4.3	82	101	0.8	1.1	1.0	1.6
T4 Interculture as in T3 + intrarow hand weeding each time	262	169	2.8	3.6	4.2	5.5	36	40	1.0	1.4	1.3	1.6
T5 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice and no weeding in lentil	178	140	3.0	2.8	4.0	4.2	112	159	0.7	1.0	1.0	1.2
T6 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice, normal tillage for lentil sowing, and preemergence application of prometryn at 0.75 kg ai/ha in lentil	189	135	3.0	2.9	4.2	4.2	92	90	1.0	1.6	1.4	1.7
T7 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice, paraquat application at 1.0 ai/ha after rice harvest, no tillage for lentil sowing, and prometryn at 0.75 kg ai/ha at preemergence in lentil	116	146	3.0	2.9	4.2	4.2	93	90	1.0	1.7	1.9	2.8
LSD (0.05)	156	99	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.9	21	35	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.8